

The Rise of Robinson Mall in Valencia City Bukidnon: Breaking Barriers of Urbanization

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ABSTRACT

Urbanization refers to general increase in population and the amount of industrialization of a settlement. It symbolizes the movement of people from rural to urban areas. Urbanization happens because of the increase in the extent and density of urban areas. Due to uncontrolled urbanization in Valencia City Bukidnon, environmental degradation has been occurring very rapidly and causing many problems like land insecurity, worsening water quality, excessive air pollution, noise and the problems of waste disposal. This paper emphasizes on the effect of urbanization on environmental components mainly public health and habitat, climate, biosphere, land and water resources. A case study of urbanization in Valencia City has been carried out leading to conclude on the existing.

INTRODUCTION

There was a big change in this world in the last century. One of which is a significant increase in the number of urban population as compared to the population in the rural areas. Barangay Bagontaas is the fourth most populous barangay in Valencia City (as of 2015). Development of the Barangay was known gradually because of the constructed Robinsons Place, Toyota Valencia, and 7-Eleven near the MVC crossing. Urbanization is a process that leads to the growth of cities due to industrialization and economic development.

In 1950, there was only 30% of the world population in urban areas, but in 2014 about 54% of the world population residing in urban areas. It means that more than half of the world population now lives in urban areas. Based on United Nation (UN, 2014), by 2050, about 66% of the world population is projected to be in urban. Increasing number of urban population have a significantly related to increasing the number of megacities in the world. With 153 million of population, there was 10 megacities in 1990, and became 28 megacities in 2014 with 453 million population which consisted of 12% urban population of the world. Asian megacities concentrate 60% of world megacities population in 2010 (Swerts and Denis, 2014) and UN (2014) projected there will be 41 urban agglomerations or megacities in 2030.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The population of Bagontaas grew from 4,112 in 1990 to 10,619 in 2015, an increase of 6,507 people. The latest census figures in 2015 denote a positive growth rate of 2.33%, or an increase of 1,211 people, from the previous population of 9,408 in 2010. Robinsons Place Valencia is said to have 6 state-of-the-art cinemas, over 200 expected tenants, and a food gallery with an area of 541 sqm with 160 seats (Project Lupad). The centerpiece design of the mall was inspired by pineapple fruit, of which the province of Bukidnon is well known of, and was built on an area of 80 thousand square meters. The interiors as well were pineapple inspired, of which the pillars of the atrium have yellow color and diamond pattern, and the seating areas were shaped like sliced pineapples.

Urbanization process has been associated with other important aspects such as economic, social, and environment. Based on UN (2014), urban living is often associated with higher levels of literacy and education, better health condition, greater access to social and economic services, and enhanced opportunities for cultural and political participation. The rapid urban growth, high population density and high consumption rate of residents in megacities has led to a wide range of local and global socioeconomic and environmental impacts which requires attention from the world community. Since it will significantly affect the global sustainability and future prosperity.

In addition with, Brian (2000) proposed urbanization issues such as: urban poverty, the rising crime rate, solid waste disposal, housing for the poor, environmental protection, pollution, and so on. are being emphasized by the government.

High population growth and rapid development in recent years has resulted in high dynamic changes of land use in most of the city. Cities have changed from small, isolated population centers to large, interconnected

economic, physical, and environmental features (Avicedo, 2013). According to Kitamura and Rustiadi (1997), the most frequent land conversion in Indonesia is from agricultural to urban uses, especially in cultivated areas around major cities.

Due to controlled urbanization in Valencia City, environmental degradation has been occurring very rapidly and causing many problems like shortage of houses, water quality, excessive air pollution, noise, dust and heat, problems of disposal of wastes, etc. which causes serious health problems. Therefore, it is a wakeup call to know and investigate the experiences of the residents in Barangay Bagontaas Valencia City, Bukidnon in the rise of Robinson Mall.

Purpose of the Study

This case study was to explore and understand the experiences of the residents of Barangay Bagontaas Valencia City Bukidnon, how they respond with the experiences, challenges and the insights shared by the residents of Barangay Bagontaas.

Specifically, this study was conceived for the purpose of giving the idea and awareness to the residents of Barangay Bagontaas Valencia City and the Local Government Unit of the City of Valencia Philippines.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the residents in Barangay Bagontaas, Valencia City, Bukidnon on the rise of Robinsons Mall?
2. What are the insights of the residents in Barangay Bagontaas, Valencia City, Bukidnon on the rise of Robinsons Mall

METHODOLOGY

Presented in this are the nature of the study, the research design used with regard to presentation, analysis and interpretation, the philosophical assumptions, research participants, role of the researcher, data sources, the data collection process, data analysis, trustworthiness which includes the following: credibility, confirmability, transferability and dependability of the study and all individuals involved and the ethical considerations in the process.

RESEARCH RESULT

Research Design

In this research study, we applied descriptive qualitative method particularly case study. According to Creswell (2009), qualitative research is a process of exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or group ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involved the emerging questions and procedure, data typically collected in the participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes and the researcher made interpretations of the meaning of the data.

Research Participants and Locale

In this case study, the participants were the residents of Barangay Bagontaas, Valencia City Bukidnon. The participants were chosen through purposive sampling which means that participants were selected because they met the preselected criteria relevant to the research question (Mack & Woodson, 2005). We personally approach them individually. Each participant was contacted. We agreed on a convenient location and time to ensure that will not be disrupted.

Picture 1. convenient location and time to ensure

In qualitative research, particularly in case study, Dukes (1984) recommends studying three (3) to five (5) subjects. Hence, we decided to pursue 4 participants in this study. We believed that this is already a considerable number of participants, adequate to give credible information and significant results and findings.

In the interview, we made sure that the ambiance was suited for the discussion and the location was free from distractions (Creswell, 2007). With that, the participants felt at ease in giving their responses. To ensure the confidentiality, we ensured that informed consent was given by them and they agreed on the ground of the interview. This was to establish the rapport between the interviewer and the participants. The names of the participants will be purposely obscured. Each participant will be given an assumed name so as not to reveal their true identities for ethical consideration.

Role of the Researcher

The researcher is known to be an instrument that cooperates and interacts with the participants in data gathering. It was my sole responsibility to maintain the smooth process and procedures in conducting this study.

The researcher is the primary data collector. Our role was to conduct the research which includes the following: gathering of information through in depth interviews and focus group discussion with the participants, observation, data interpretation and analysis, creating conclusions and recommendations, and lastly, present the research study to the panelists.

Data Sources

According to Creswell (2007), sources of qualitative data are typically gathered in multiple forms such as interviews, observations and documentation. In this study, the data was taken from the participants' experiences and observations which were obtained through In-depth Interview. The setting for

these sources of data was in the Barangay Bagontaas where the participants are currently residing in that area.

Aside of from writing responses of the participants, voice recorder was used to make sure that the responses will not be misinterpreted. The written and recorded responses were analyzed carefully. Moreover, the researcher formulated the guide questions. The guide questions were aligned to the statement of the problem to attain the purpose of the study.

Data Collection Procedure

This qualitative research took comprehensive and methodical procedures to achieve its purpose. Creswell (2007) mentioned that qualitative researchers will be tied up in a series of activities in the process of collecting data. A vital step is to find participants involve in this study, the availability of material, place where to conduct study to obtain accurate information.

As a researchers, we took rigorous steps in the data collection procedure. we engaged in series of activities in the process of collecting data before arriving to the completion of the research study. First, to acquire permission to have access to my potential participants, we sought permission from the Barangay Captain of Bagontaas with a request letter.

Second, participants were identified through purposive sampling. Participants were identified and listed as recommended by the residents of Barangay Bagontaas. Consent forms were given and explained to the participants.

Third, interview took place in the specified time and venue only after the participants have signed the consent and were informed of the objective of the study. We used my prepared open-ended questions to personally conduct the individual face to face interview. Cellular phone and other gadgets were used to ensure validity and reliability which are very significant in the conduct of the study.

Fourth, answers were transcribed verbatim to ensure a greater degree of accuracy during the data analysis. Fifth, thematic analysis was done.

Data Analysis

Before the data was analyzed, all in-depth interviews were gathered and translated into written form for a closer study. The process of transcribing helped me to have a deep understanding of the data gathered as it encompasses what will be represented in the transcript.

Afterwards, the next move was to categorize the information. The objective is to identify any patterns representing the concepts of the participants during the data collection phase. Data analysis as mentioned by Goodyear & Hativa (2002) is the most complex and mysterious of all of the phases of a qualitative project and the one that receives the least thoughtful discussion in the literature.

This study made use of the thematic analysis in analyzing the collected and gathered data. The objective is to identify any patterns representing the concepts of the participants during the data collection phase. Specific codes were

developed allowing me to categorize the responses into the above-mentioned construct, while identifying emergent themes.

Trustworthiness of the Study

Trustworthiness is the quality in a study when the data collected is generally applicable and consistent. Data is applicable when the reader become familiar with the study and assess whether the setting and results will transfer to their particular setting or future research study. The applicability of this study relied on the thick description of the observations, settings, and participants that we provided. To ensure consistency of this study, there must be continuation in collecting data until the point of saturation (Lofland & Lofland, 2005).

We addressed trustworthiness of our findings by employing the different strategies to meet the four concerns of trustworthiness that call consideration: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Shenton, 2004). Trustworthiness is the quality achieved in the study if the data collected is applicable and consistent. Trustworthiness of a qualitative study can be improved keeping great credibility and objectivity (Gay & Airasians, 2003).

To address credibility, we employed the following techniques: First, we developed an early familiarity with the culture of the participants before collection. It was achieved during the preliminary visits. Letters were sent to the Barangay Captain stating the purpose of the study. And, we identified the participants in their respective Barangay. It is very important that the researcher developed a good rapport to the teacher-participant so that accurate information will be gathered. This was stressed by Shenton (2004) saying that these methods are useful to saturate data.

Transferability is defined as the potential for the results of one setting to be transferred to other settings. This is very important when deciding if the results may be useful in another research setting. It implied generalizability of the findings and results of the study to other settings, situations, populations, and circumstances. This is the quality we have been calling "external validity" or "generalizability" in our use of the term in the introduction to research design. Transferability in the naturalistic researcher maintains that no true generalization is really possible; all observations are defined by the specific contexts in which they occur (Lincoln & Guba, 2000).

To address transferability in our study, the interviewees answered transcripts and data analysis of documents were included in Appendices that served as reference. All peripherals such as hard and soft copies were kept as verification for further studies.

On the other hand, dependability is an assessment of the quality of the integrated processes of data collection, data analysis, and theory generation. In order to address the dependability issue more directly, the processes within the study were reported in detail, thereby enabling a future researcher to repeat the work, if not necessarily to gain the same result. Moreover, audit trail was included. It consists of original transcripts, analysis and documents.

Confirmability as defined by Cohen & Crabtree (2008) is a degree of neutrality or the extent to which findings of the study are shaped by the participants and not researcher bias, motivation or interest. Confirmability is a

measure of how well inquiry's findings are supported by the data collected (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In order to ensure confirmability in our study, member checking was done and validation form and sheets for accuracy were attached. We also showed that the results are clearly linked to the conclusions in a way that can be followed and replicated (Moon et al., 2016).

Ethical Consideration

To establish ethical considerations, we followed the ethical steps as suggested by King and Horrocks (1998) such as respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent and confidentiality. Ethics has become a cornerstone for conducting effective and meaningful research (Drew, 2007). The participants of the study are individuals who are under my protection, so I developed trust among us. As stressed by Neuman (2006) in writing a research, the examiner must yield into credit the numerous ethical issues, concerns, dilemmas and conflicts that happen during the process. Ethics defines what is or are not authentic to do or what appropriate research technique absorbs. It is often a steadiness balance between two values; the quest of scientific knowledge and the privileges of those being studied.

To establish **respect for persons**, we asked permission from the Barangay Captain of Bagontaas for to us be able to proceed to the study. The participants were given an informed consent so that their willingness to get involved in the study was sought. Respect for persons is an obligation of the researcher not to exploit the weakness of the participants.

To establish **beneficence**, we asked their vacant time for the in-depth interview and their preferred place where they can freely express their thoughts about the study. Each of them was given the informed consent before the set date and time of the in-depth interview. Beneficence requires a commitment of minimizing the risks of the participants rather maximizing the profits that are due to them (Creswell, 2012).

To establish **confidentiality**, we ensured that the true identities of the participants were hidden. In the study, to protect the identity and anonymity of our participants, we used aliases instead their names during the interview and in the transcription. Privacy with respect to information the key informants disclosed during participation in the study will be protected within the limits of the law.

To establish **justice**, we made sure that the participants do not spend any amount for we acknowledged their contribution to complete my study. The participants were accommodated properly. Participants of the qualitative research were given due credits for all their contributions.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the researcher presents, analyzes and interprets the data gathered in textual and tabular forms. This part of the study is also concerned mainly on the results obtained from the responses of the participants in the in-depth interview. We analyzed their responses and drew out the themes which

emerged from the core ideas. The core ideas came from the responses of the participants.

The focus of this discussion is on the positive and negative experiences encountered by the residents in Barangay Bagontaas, Valencia City on the rise of the Robinson Mall. In addition, struggles encountered by the residents would speak of their perceptions and insights of the experience. Most of the residents' experiences are alike. The reason for this is that most of their experiences in the establishment of Robinson Mall are quite similar since all the residents have positive feedbacks.

Table 1. The Experiences of the residents on the Rise of Robinsons Mall in Valencia City, Bukidnon

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Improper Segregation of Solid Waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solid wastes are not properly segregated • No proper and permanent garbages
Job Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents are given the first priority to be hired and work in the mall • Low unemployment rate in the Barangay Bagontaas
Economic Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases the income of the Barangay Bagontaas • Additional income of the Barangay Bagontaas

Improper Segregation of Solid Waste

Solid waste management is a worldwide phenomenon. Improper management of solid waste (SW) causes hazards to inhabitants. It is a big challenge all over the world for human beings. The problem of solid waste management (SWM) is also prevailing in the urban environment. Romeo, a barangay captain participant, voiced out his sentiments on the improper segregation of solid waste by the management of Robinson Mall. He mentioned that:

“Ahm... ang ilahang basura kay wala nila na tarong ug segregate. Sagul-sagol ang ilahang pagbutang sa mga basura like, papel, mga plastic, empty bottles, malate, basa, ug mga uga ug uban pa....”

On the other hand, Sheila, a vendor participant, shared her experience and observation in the improper segregation of garbages. She stated that:

“Ang ilahang basura wala na segregate ang mga plastics, papel, mga malate ug di-malata, uga ug mga baa. Ahmm.. kanang bisan asa lng ni pod ibutang ang basula nila walay sakto na area.”

Similarly, Ana, a barangay kagawad participant, also shared the same experiences that improper segregation of solid waste may lead into diseases of the residents in Bagontaas. She disclosed that:

“Ah.. ahm.. ang ilahang basura gyod kay dili maayo pagkabutang tungod kay ilang gi sagul-sagol ang tanang basura. Example, ang mga malate ug di-malata, plastics, papel, cellophanes, ug uban pa. Ang nakita ug na obserba nga dili jud xa maayo tungod kay isa siya sa mga makahatag ug sakit sa mga lumulupyo sa Barangay Bagontaas.”

Based on the responses of the participants, it is noted that Robinsons Mall in Barangay Bagontaas, Valencia City, Bukidnon had an improper segregation of solid waste. With these, it could lead into hazards in the human health of the people living near the area.

Job Opportunities

With an ever-growing global population have come changes in the way that cities emerge and develop, with urbanization being one of the most prominent. As cities grow in population, they also tend to grow in physical size and expand outwards. This expansion is apparent as the majority of the world's urban population lives in cities and towns. It offers more job opportunities to the people living in a certain area. Romeo, a barangay captain participant, detailed that:

“Sukad nga natukod kining Robinsons Mall diri sa amoang barangay, daghan ang natabangan ug natagaan ug trabaho nga mga lumulupyo. Hilabi na gayod ang atong mga kaissoonan nga wala nakahuman ug college naka-apply sila ug trabaho sa Mall. Kini usa ka dakong tabang sa among mga constituents sa maong lugar. Ako jud gi emphasize sa tag-iya nga first priority ang mga lumulupyo sa among barangay nga ilang dawaton para matagaan ug trabaho labi na kadtong naglisod. Ning baba pod ang unemployment rate sukad na nay mall diri sa among dapit.”

Ana, also shared a comparable experiences. She shared that; the urbanization of a place could offer more job opportunities to the people. It could help them to elevate their way of life especially those who have family and also it is the solution to answer their problem in terms of financial aspect. She narrated that:

“Sa pagtukod aning Robinson Mall, nakahatag kini ug dakong oportunidad sa mga tao dinhi sa amoang lugar sa Bagontaas tungod kay daghan ang wala makahuman ug eskwela sa kolehiyo tungod sa financial nga problema sa pamilya. Ug base sa datos namo, nabawasan ang unemployment rate sa among lugar because the the mall nga naa nag operate sa amoa. Kini tubag sa problema sa mga pamilya nga dunay financial problem..ahm.. Kini pod makatabang para ma-elevate ang panginabuhi sa uban. ANg among mga sakop diri nga lumulupyo sa barangay ang gitagaan ug first priority nga maka work ug e hire sa trabaho, mao kana ang among nasabutan sa tag-iya or manager sa mall.”

Cyril, a manager of the Robinson Mall participant, also shared the same opinion with regards to the rise of Robinson Mall in the area and stated that:

“The rise of the Robinson Mall in this Barangay gave more job opportunities to the people. The people living in this barangay are the first priority to be given the chance to work and be hired since we agreed with the officials. And aside from that, dako siya ug tabang hilabi na kadtong mga estudyante nga wala makahuman sa ilang pag-eskwela sa kolehiyo maka-apply sila ug trabaho nga makatabang sa ilang panginahanglan sa ilang pamilya. At least in terms of financial aspect it could also elevate their way of life.”

With these responses, it could be seen that the rise of the Robinson Mall in Barangay Bagontaas could really help alleviate the lifestyle of the people because job is an important factor and without work life is impossible. With job we can do everything, either fulfill our desires or family needs but the important one is we eventually attain confidence, self-respect & social status which makes us feel the part of society.

Economic Development

The emphasis of this discussion is on the growth of Barangay Bagontaas area as one of the most important characteristics of spatial development in Valencia City, Bukidnon during the past decades and is traditionally described with a few indicators on a relatively coarse spatial scale. However, urbanization is not only a matter of land use change, but also socio-economic changes, which may or may not manifest itself as physical changes in built-up area and land use. Through the rise of Robinson Mall it has great help especially in the economic development/status in the barangay. Romeo, a barangay captain participant, shared how the rise of Robinson Mall really contribute to the economic development and income, he verbalized:

“Tungod aning Robinson Mall nga natukod sa among lugar, dako siya ug tabang sa barangay labi na gayod sa income kay tungod ang mga trabahante nga na hired nila manguha man ug mga requirements, so.... Makadungag jud siya sa among kaban financial na panudlanan. Isa pa tungod pod sa mga taxes nga ilahang ginabayad sa amoa. Maka generate jud mi ug additional income sa barangay nga pwed namo magamit sa amoang mga projects para sa mga katawhan.

In the in-depth interview, manager participant, Cyril, made mention how Robinson Mall additionally increases the income of Barangay Bagontaas. She stated that:

“Because of the rise of Robinson Mall in this barangay, nakatabang pod mi sa pag increase sa ilahang kaban or income. Tungod kay ang among mga empleyado magkuha man ug mga requirements sama sa cedula, ug barangay clearance nga kinahanglan namo usa sila madawat sa trabaho.”

Further, another vendor participant, Sheila, also shared how Robinson Mall support and give additional income in our barangay, she voiced out:

“Kanang...ahm... Kaning Robinsons Mall nakatabang jud ug dako sa amoang barangay labi na sa income naka dungag siya sa among pundo kay tungod ang mga aplikante nga na hired sa mall manguha man sa ilahang mga requirements labi na cedula ug barangay clearance. Nakatabang pod sa paglago sa among turismo ug nagtaas ang among era sa barangay.”

Thus, urbanization really helps to generate employment, wealth and productivity growth, which is the major force in the economic development. It also combats poverty by promoting

Insights of the residents in Barangay Bagontaas, Valencia City, Bukidnon on the rise of Robinsons Mall

One of the most important thing to consider in the urbanization is how does a certain barangay is well-develop and progressive. A progressive barangay where the residents are provided of the basic needs such as security, good sanitation and proper waste management.

Table 2. The Insights of the residents on the rise of Robinsons Mall in Valencia City, Bukidnon

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Progressive Barangay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A growing and developing barangay in the next few years • More investor and establishments will come in
Efficient Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick and accessible for the consumer • Easy and Comfortable for the consumers

Progressive Barangay

Urbanization is not about simply increasing the number of urban residents or expanding the area of cities. More importantly, it’s about a complete change from rural style in terms of industry structures, employment, living environment, social security and progress. Leo, an engineer participant, verbalized that:

“The rise of the Robinsons Mall isa ka tmailhan nga maging progreso ug molambo pa gayod ang barangay ug mas the more pa ang development sa umaabot nga panahon. Aside ana, daghan pang mga establishments’ ang matukod diring dapita ug daghan na mga investors’ ang mudagsa.”

In the in-depth interview, barangay captain participant, Romeo, made mention that in order for a barangay or even municipality to improve when it comes to development it must be progressive on. He stated divulge that:

“Para sa akoa, ang isa ka barangay nga matawag nato nga progresso kuni adunay mga daghan ug paspas nga development. Usa pa ani mao ang daghan nga mga investors mo patukod ug

mga establishments sa umaabot nga panahon. Kana matawag nato nga there is already progress in a certain barangay."

Further, Sheila a barangay kagawad participant added that:

"For me progress in a municipality or even in a barangay is one of the main target of every officials. Makaingon ko nga ang is aka barangay progresso kung adunay mga daghang establishments nga nag operate ug daghan mga investors. I am looking forward for this in the next years to come here in our barangay nga daghan pang mga mo invest ug motukod sa ilang mga establishments para mas daghan pa pod pa tagaan ug trabaho."

Efficient Services

One of the most important reasons in the rise of Robinson Mall in a particular place is to have very easy, comfortable and manageable access especially in buying things that you needed most. It is voiced out by Romeo, a barangay captain participant that:

"Ah.. ang pagtukod aning Robinsons Mall diri sa barangay us aka dako tabang para mas madali ug accessible sa akua ug sa mga tao nga taga diri. Kay kung naa kay paliton dali ra kaau dili na nimo kailangan muadto pa sa is aka lugar para mamalit sa mall mas wasy ug comfortable ka unya duol lang sa imong balay. Malipayon kayo mi nga natukod ni ang mall diri sa amoang barangay."

Ana, a vendor, also mentioned that:

"Ako isip usa ka lumulupyo aning barangay, nalipay kayo ko nga nay mall natukod diria tungod kay mas dali, easy ug comfortable ka mamalit. Dili kinahanglan pa nga muadto pa sa laing dapit para mamalit. Makauli pa ka dayon sa balay labi na kung ikaw nagdali-dali ug daghan trabho or something emergency."

Sheila, a barangay kagawad participant is agreeable with this and stated that:

"Dako kaau akong pasalamat nga adunay mall diri sa among barangay kay mas madali ug dli naka kinahanglan muadto pa sa laing lugar para mamalit tungod naa naman mall diria duol sa amoa. Isa pa, mas accessible ug komportable ka isip us aka mamalitay kay dali ra para sa imoha."

Cyril, a manager, in an in-Depth Interview participant, also shared the same opinion with regards to the rise of Robinson mall and divulged that:

"Sa akong nakita ug na obserbahan, sukad naa nay mall diri sa barangay o lugar sa bagontaas, mas mapadali, sayon, ug comfortable ang mga mamalitay tungod kay accessible ra man kaau sa ilaha ug mas mapadali ang serbisyo nga mahatag. Sa mga nadungog nako na mga feedback gikan sa mga consumers, mas ganahan sila ug nalipay tungod kay dli na magsliod ug palit sa mga palitonon kay naa nay mall."

Thus, the participants' responses made me realize that the rise of Robinsons Mall gives them an easy access and efficient services in everything

that they do. It has an impact on the way of living of the people in the municipality or in the barangay.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From this, we can conclude that some causes of damage to the environment due to urbanization lies in the legislation and the regulating agencies in the place. Serious attention should be given to the need for improving urban strategies, which promote efficiency in resource use.

Urgent attention should be given to reduce the generation of solid waste at the sources through mandatory standards and regulation fee and tax incentives, and education and voluntary compliance. In case adequate steps are not taken to prevent pollution and to improve the quality of life by providing more social amenities, the life of the urban dwellers of Barangay Bagontaas specifically the management of Robinson Place Mall may become more miserable this that cause of health hazards and worst devastation.

So, this is the responsibility of government take necessary steps to prevent the environment by taking plausible solutions and also the planners should also concentrate on these views while planning and protect the environment.

Furthermore, we believed that this study will lead to the improvement and impact of environmental issues in the rise of Robinson Place Mall in Valencia City.

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